

**“ANALYSES OF THE HEROES” IN THE NOVEL “ORLANDO” BY
VIRGINIA WOOLF.**

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the analysis of the heroes. The essence of these heroes is described by well-known novelist Virginia Woolf in his work “Orlando”.

Key words: Protagonist, antagonist, static character, flat character, dynamic character, round character, underdog character.

Introduction: Adeline Virginia Woolf who is an English writer also, considered one of the most important modernist among 20th century authors and a pioneer in the use of stream of consciousness as a narrative tool. She published her first work, *The Voyage*, in the publishing house of her half-brother. The best and famous works she wrote include novels such as *To the Lighthouse*, *Orlando*, and *Mrs. Dalloway*. She is also well-known for her critical writings or essays *A Room of One’s Own* in which she advocates the women writers saying, “A woman must have money and a room of her own if she is to write fiction”¹. The distinctive features of Woolf’s fiction have tended to obscure her essential strength: after Elizabeth Browning is another lyrical novelist in English Literature. She wrote a tentative

¹ Virginia_Woolf_-_A_Room_of_Ones_Own. 4thpage.

novel: sometimes, a narrative is commonplace and uneventful, while sometimes it is dissolved in the receptive consciousness of the characters. In her writings, visual and auditory impressions are created by the fusion of stylistic virtuosity and intense lyricism. The poetic vision of Virginia Woolf's novels is so intense that it elevates the ordinary and commonplace settings, even the war-time setting in most of her novels.

A Biography is a novel by Virginia Woolf, first published on 11 October 1928. Inspired by the tumultuous family history of the aristocratic poet and novelist Vita Sackville-West, Woolf's lover and close friend, it is arguably one of her most popular novels; *Orlando* is a history of English literature in satiric form. The book describes the adventures of a poet who changes sex from man to woman and lives for centuries, meeting the key figures of English literary history. Considered a feminist classic, the book has been written about extensively by scholars of women's writing and gender and transgender studies.² The eponymous hero is born as a male nobleman in England during the reign of Elizabeth I. He undergoes a mysterious change of sex at the age of about 30 and lives on for more than 300 years into modern times without ageing perceptibly.

Literature review: I am going to state some others' attitude to this work. A literary critique of *Orlando* on an onomastic and psychological basis was conducted by the historian and Italianist Alessio Bologna in his book: Alessio Bologna, *L'Orlando ariostesco in Virginia Woolf*, in Id., *Studi di letteratura "popolare" e onomastica tra Quattro e Cinquecento*, Pisa, ETS 2007, pp. 75-85 ("Nominatio. Collana di Studi Onomastici").

The skating party on the Thames was featured in *Simple Gifts*, a Christmas collection of six animated shorts shown on PBS in 1977.

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Orlando:_A_Biography

The 1981 film Freak Orlando, by German artist, writer, and director Ulrike Ottinger, is an adaptation of the story, blending it with aspects of Tod Browning's 1931 seminal horror film, Freaks.

The novel has been adapted for theatre and film. In 1989 the American director Robert Wilson, and writer Darryl Pinckney collaborated on a theatrical production. A British film adaptation was released in 1992, starring Tilda Swinton as Orlando and Quentin Crisp as Queen Elizabeth I.

A second theatre adaptation of Orlando, by Sarah Ruhl, was first presented by the Piven Theatre Workshop in Evanston, Illinois in 1998.³ It was presented by The Actors' Gang Theater in Los Angeles in 2003.⁴ The play premiered Off-Broadway in New York in 2010. It subsequently premiered for the Sydney Theatre Company in Australia at the Sydney Opera House starring Jacqueline McKenzie in the title role. In 2016, composer Peter Aderhold and librettist Sharon L. Joyce premiered an opera based on the work at the Braunschweig State Theater, as well as an opera by Olga Neuwirth, premiered in the Vienna State Opera in December 2019.

The League of Extraordinary Gentlemen comics feature Orlando, starting with a mention in The New Traveller's Almanac and short story and cameo in Black Dossier. Orlando is then featured as a main character in Volume III: Century and Volume IV: The Tempest.

On November 5, 2019, the BBC News listed Orlando on its list of the 100 most influential novels.⁵

A new theatre adaptation by Neil Bartlett, directed by Michael Grandage, and starring Emma Corrin is set to open in London's West End in autumn 2022.⁶

³ Hayford, Justin (11 June 1998). "Orlando". Chicago Reader. Retrieved 19 December 2018.

⁴ Nichols, David C. (7 March 2003). "'Orlando' is ageless at Actors' Gang". Los Angeles Times. Retrieved 19 October 2020.

⁵ "100 'most inspiring' novels revealed by BBC Arts". BBC News. 5 November 2019. Retrieved 10 November 2019. The

⁶ "Orlando - Emma Corrin plays the title role". London Box Office. 1 August 2022. Retrieved 1 September 2022.

Analysis: A major theme in the novel is the idea that fulfillment is almost impossible to achieve. Time and time again, Orlando tries to find meaning in life and happiness by trying to immerse himself in various activities. He finds soon enough that the pleasures of literature, women, and good company last only for a short period of time; after the initial thrill disappears, what is left behind is an emptiness that is harder to fill than before. In this way, the novel presents Orlando's continuous quest for happiness and pleasure. Writing, especially writing poetry, is Orlando's life passion. When the reader meets Orlando as a boy of sixteen, he is said to already be a prolific writer; he especially likes to write about nature, though he finds it hard to write about nature when actually looking at it. Orlando's writing style changes throughout his/her lifetime and is influenced by the trends of society and the people with whom s/he interacts. For example, the biographer notes that Orlando got better at writing witty, natural dialogue after spending time with Pope, Addison, and Swift. Of the shifts in Orlando's writing, the biographer writes, "She had been a gloomy boy, in love with death, as boys are; and then she had been amorous and florid; and then she had been sprightly and satirical; and sometimes she had tried prose and sometimes she had tried drama. Yet through all these changes she had remained, she reflected, fundamentally the same" (208). This quote demonstrates that Woolf believes writing is inextricably tied to one's personality and experiences. While Orlando feels ashamed of her writing for a long period due to Nicholas Greene's scorn, she is eventually lauded as a great author and wins The Burdett Coutts' Memorial Prize for the poem she spent her whole life on, "The Oak Tree." Nicholas Greene seems to like "The Oak Tree" for its emulation of styles of past authors Orlando read and spent time with; his character serves to show that people, especially literary critics, will always nostalgically idolize writing of the past. One might think that at the time Orlando was published, the most disruptive, anachronistic aspect of the novel would be the title character's bending of gender and societal norms, or perhaps Woolf's critiques of high society and the literary

world. However, the focus of Cleveland B. Chase's New York Times review of Orlando in October of 1928 focuses on Woolf's depiction of time. He writes, "Not that she has abandoned the 'stream of consciousness' method which she used with such conspicuous success in her previous novels, but with it she has combined what, for lack of a better term, we might describe as an application to writing of the Einstein theory of relativity. In this new work she is largely preoccupied with the "time" element in character and human relationships, and with a statement of the exact complexion of that intangible moment, a combination of past and future, of objective reality and subjective consciousness, which we refer to as the present" (Mrs. Woolf Explores the "Time" Element). While the reviewer opines that this choice "left the book perhaps more confused than was strictly necessary," Woolf explores the concept of time in a quite purposeful way throughout the novel. She tells us that some hours in Orlando's life flash by while others contain decades, simply because of the events or intellectual work done within the period of time. Orlando ages slowly, transforms into a woman at middle age and experiences a rebirth of sorts as a result, and continues to age even more slowly so that, after over 400 years, she remains a thriving, healthy adult woman. Woolf's choice to span such a vast period of English history allows the reader to compare not only the experiences of men and women in England but also the effect of different eras on the freedom and agency of women.⁷

Discussion: Orlando's journey, from the court of Queen Elizabeth I to modern times will also be an internal one. He is an impulsive poet who learns patience in matters of the heart, and a woman who knows what it is to be a man. Virginia's Woolf's most unusual and fantastic creation is a funny, exuberant tale which examines the very nature of sexuality. "For it would seem - her case proved it - that we write, not with the fingers, but with the whole person. The nerve which controls the pen winds itself about every fibre of our being, threads the heart, pierces the liver."

⁷ <https://www.gradesaver.com/orlando/study-guide/themes>

— Virginia Woolf, "Orlando: A Biography"

Orlando (1992): "Is this the ultimate 'have your cake and eat it' when it comes to film costumes? Not only do we get to see Tilda Swinton in doublet and hose as a beautiful young Elizabethan nobleman, in powdered wig and greatcoat as the Restoration war hero, but we also see her in taffeta as an Augustan era lady, in a crinoline as a Victorian widow and in her civvies as a wartime mother. And she's perfectly kitted out as each – as is Quentin Crisp as Elizabeth I. What an amazing piece of casting."

Conclusion: As this study has shown, *Orlando* and *Flush* both display three important hallmarks of postmodern fiction: a concern for historiography, extensive use of parody, and the denaturalization of cultural assumptions. While demonstrating the presence of these characteristics in Woolf's fictional biographies helps answer the question of how these works are postmodern, it does not fully address the important question of why. To answer that question, these postmodern traits must be examined together. When considered together, these characteristics illustrate how *Orlando* and *Flush* represent a fundamental departure from the epistemological position of modernism to the ontological position of postmodernism. In other words, these traits do not denote postmodernism, but taken together, they reveal a philosophy and method in Woolf's work that is ontological at its core.

Finally, Woolf's feminism must be recognized as a crucial influence on the postmodern positions taken in *Orlando* and *Flush*. Her awareness of the inadequacies of historical representation and of the impact of cultural assumptions are, to a large extent, a direct result of her own experience with misrepresentations of women and the false cultural assumptions made about them. Just as they express postmodern attitudes, both *Orlando* and *Flush* exhibit clear feminist sentiments. For example, the motivation behind denaturalizing assumptions about sexual difference and the subversion of the "great men" standard in these works is often as much feminist as

postmodern. This does not, however, mean that it must be either feminist or postmodern. On the contrary, Woolf's possible feminist interests in *Orlando* and *Flush* intersect with postmodern interests in historiography, representation, and narrativity. Ultimately it is unnecessary, and perhaps impossible, to label the points where these influences intersect as either postmodern or feminist. Instead, it is best to view them as mutually reinforcing sets of principles that, at least in *Orlando* and *Flush*, work toward common goals. After all, Woolf's next major work after *Orlando* was *A Room of One's Own*, a classic of feminist discourse. Ultimately, Woolf's feminism, when combined with her interest in biography and her need for a break from modernist composition, laid the foundation for the postmodern positions expressed in the fictional biographies, and, in turn, her feminism was further refined as a result of her work on *Orlando* and *Flush*. Finally, one question remains to be answered: why does this study's examination of the postmodernist traits in *Orlando* and *Flush* matter? This study shares a goal espoused by Pamela L. Caughie in her book *Virginia Woolf and Postmodernism*: to provide "a perspective that can free Woolf's writings from the cage of modernism and the camps of feminism without denying these relations in her texts" (Caughie 2). As this study and broader conversations about postmodernism in Woolf reveal, Woolf's fiction contains more than a purely modernist or feminist reading could ever uncover. She is absolutely both a modernist and feminist, and the 52 contributions she made in these capacities are immeasurable. However, circumscribing Woolf to any particular role obscures the full endowment that her genius offers. Only by continuing to explore the vast territory of inspiration that her work opens to us can we ensure ourselves of the full benefits of her singular brilliance.

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